

Does Virtual Reality Influence Stress Appearance?

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***Abstract:* Virtual reality has become an extremely relevant topic in today's world, used in a variety of applications and industries such as entertainment, education, medicine, and training. Understanding how virtual environments affect mental health and human emotions is an important area of research to understand the potential challenges and benefits of this technology. In this study, we will examine the results of EEG measurement to detect stress during virtual reality use. To this end, we reviewed four recent studies, all of which concluded that there are indicators suggestive of stress.**

Introduction

Since the emergence of virtual reality (VR) in recent years, it has experienced a huge surge in popularity, becoming a revolutionary technology that allows users to not only experience immersive, computer-simulated environments but also access them via social media. Virtual reality has a multitude of applications in a wide range of industries, from gaming and learning to rehabilitation and workplace training. Even though this technology has brought innovation and transformative experiences to users, the question arises as to whether it could also increase stress levels. For the further development of VR, it is important to recognize the stress effects associated with it. It is therefore important that people who engage with it have a sense of well-being.

When using virtual reality, users experience many emotions. Some studies have proven that the use of virtual reality evokes emotional states [1, 2]. Despite the positive aspects that have emerged in many studies, it is necessary

to know some other aspects that may occur due to the complexity of the structure of virtual reality and the difficulty of measuring these cases [3]. Several human body signals can be used to measure the effects of virtual reality, including motion sickness, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), electrogastrography (EGG), electrocardiography (ECG), heart rate variability (HRV), and galvanic skin response (GSR) [4, 5]. An electroencephalogram is a recording method that records the electrical activity of the brain to monitor its electrophysiological activity [5]. The main aim of this study is therefore to find out whether there is a relationship between virtual reality games and stress.

Materials and Methods

In this study, we used the literature analysis method, which involves collecting publications on a specific topic from various databases. During the process, some specific criteria can also be defined. It is the most widely used method of literature review. We performed the following steps in the literature search: (i) defining the topic, (ii) investigating related topics, and (iii) conducting the analysis. In this section, we will explain the steps we took to review previous studies on virtual reality and stress.

The main aim of writing research questions is to justify the rationale for the research and review of studies. Research questions also help with data collection [6]. Our research question (RQ) is: *Does VR affect the occurrence of stress?* The studies to be reviewed were identified through title search for the terms: “virtual reality” or “VR”, AND “electroencephalography” or “EEG” AND “stress” in the Web of Science database. The result was five articles that included stress, virtual reality, and EEG in their title. We excluded one article because it did not meet our criteria. One of the conditions is that they must be freely accessible, and we did not set a condition on the year of publication.

Discussion

In this section, we will discuss four selected articles and explain the steps they followed. In the first study by (Fadeev et al., 2020) [7], three women were selected as participants who underwent stressful virtual reality scenarios while their electroencephalogram (EEG) and autonomic nervous system were monitored. Virtual reality can induce acute stress reactions, activate the sympathetic nervous system, and decrease the activity of the parasympathetic nervous system. EEG power decreases with the high-stress response; however, the alpha wave of the EEG increases when the avoidance response

is triggered. As a result, the use of stressful VR content can lead to severe emotional stress in a user; therefore, limitations must be considered.

The second article is by Kamińska et al. [8], who created an acquisition protocol using an EEG headset to monitor the subject's psychophysical state, alternating between stressful and relaxing scenes in the form of an interactive simulation of virtual reality. The Stroop test was used as a stressor, and the relaxation scenes were developed using scenarios developed for bilateral stimulation psychotherapy. Twenty-eight healthy adult volunteers working in an office took part in a virtual reality session as part of the experiment. The subjects' EEG signals were continuously recorded using the EMOTIV EPOC Flex wireless EEG head cap system. The subjects were asked to fill out surveys about their stress level and current mood after the session. After classifying the stress level using a convolutional neural network (CNN), they compared the effectiveness of the classification with conventional methods.

The third article we reviewed is from Aspiotis et al. [9]. In this study, a VR headset was used in conjunction with a state-of-the-art electrocardiography (ECG) sensor and a wearable EEG device to induce stress in high mountain scenarios while performing real-time monitoring of EEG and ECG biomarkers. The EEG data, which were contaminated by motion noise, were preprocessed using a reliable signal-cleaning pipeline. To investigate how these biomarkers relate to stress, statistical and correlation analyses were performed. Based on differences in heart rate increase, twenty-one participants (ranging from 20 to 27 years of age; 8 females and 13 males) with normal or corrected to normal vision were chosen for this experiment. The participant pool was split into two groups, from which statistically significant differences in EEG biomarkers were observed. Finally, changes in occipital asymmetry and band power were connected to stress related to height and beta and gamma band brain activation, which is consistent with the findings of the self-reported Perceived Stress Scale questionnaire.

The final article we chose was written by Ji et al. [10]. They designed Reich Chancellery which is currently in a state of ruin. The Reich Chancellery's interior was divided into areas with high and low ceilings. This study used brain wave experiments to investigate how a person's emotions changed about ceiling height while they were moving to determine the stress index for each building space. They chose one 38-year-old male subject for this experiment. Virtual reality was used to recreate the Reich Chancellery, and first and second analyses were performed on the brain wave data gathered for each space. In the first analysis, the space with the highest fluctuation was examined, and beta wave changes in the stress index were computed. In the

second analysis, deep-learning algorithms were used to verify accuracy and examine areas with a high-stress index. The change in stress index scores was the highest when entering from the 15 m floor height to the 3 m floor height. The correlation between ten distinct types of brain waves and waveforms was examined.

To explain and understand the signals sent by the brain, we will explain how they are translated by each wave according to [11-13].

1. Delta: Sleep deeply without dreaming. Too high levels can indicate a brain injury, but also an illness. Learning difficulties are an indicator of delta. A lack of content can lead to an inability to become enlightened.

2. Theta: Most sleepers have it. They can occur when you are concentrating and meditating deeply, but also in emotionally stressful situations such as hopelessness, impulsivity, hyperactivity, and depression. When theta waves are visible, inattention is detected; when they are suppressed, tension, low emotional awareness, and anxiety can be detected.

3. Alpha: Alpha waves, which indicate a relaxed state, occur shortly before falling asleep and immediately after waking up. They also have to do with the mental state of introspection, concentrated reflection on a subject, and creative thinking. They indicate health, serenity, and optimistic thinking. In ERP studies (event-related potentials), they are present in a resting position with closed eyelids. When performing mathematical processes or other tasks that require greater mental effort, they disappear. Anxiety, high levels of stress, and insomnia may indicate too little of it, while inattention and excessive relaxation may indicate too much content.

4. Beta 0: The state of heightened alertness, mental activity, and focus of attention. In general, low-amplitude beta waves can be a sign of sadness, anxiety, and problems with concentration and dreaming. An excessive amount of content is associated with tension, anxiety, and the inability to relax.

5. Beta 1: A state of extreme concentration and alertness, rational thinking, and emotional restraint.

6. Beta 2: A state of heightened mental activity, anxiety, excitement, and irritability. In a healthy person, this could be an indication of panic.

7. Gamma: Several studies show that the amplitude of these waves increases as the subject focuses on the stimulus source. The gamma wave has a short duration of a few dozen milliseconds. A high number of them could be a sign of stress, anxiety, and restlessness; a low number could be a sign of depression or learning difficulties.

Table 1 summarizes the types of different EEG waves.

Table 1. Summary of the type of waves detected while using VR in each article.

No.	Article	Results
1	[7]	The alpha rhythm was low in some scenarios, and it appeared clearly in the stress scenarios. the power of theta rhythm was high in rest conditions.
2	[8]	Beta 1 appeared after doing specific tasks that need attention and concentration,
3	[9]	They observed the presence of occipital alpha asymmetry during the stressful part of the experimental process. it was discovered that changes in occipital asymmetry and band power were connected to stress related to height and beta and gamma band brain activation
4	[10]	Correlation of parameters when alpha, theta, delta, and gamma waves were used along with the beta wave. The results showed that the stress indices were intensely high.

Based on the summaries of the results in the four research studies, it appears that there was some level of anxiety present. This is evident from the fact that gamma waves appear in one result. Gamma waves are typically associated with high-level cognitive processes such as concentration and higher-order thinking and could be a sign of stress. It is also important to note that the nature of the experimental setup had a significant impact on the type of brainwave patterns observed using EEG analysis. Whether it was a virtual reality game; or a specific environment used as a stimulus in research, it influenced the pattern of brain activity and the waves detected which can be clear in [7-10]. Alpha, beta 0, and beta 1 could be a sign of stress according to [11-13] with different levels, and this is referred to focusing on VR environment senses [10] or doing mental activities [8]. This emphasizes the importance of examining the context and environmental factors surrounding the experiments to understand their impact on the EEG results. The presence of brainwave patterns such as alpha and beta waves indicates that the mind was active and possibly operating at a higher level of concentration. Beta waves are typically associated with states that require high levels of concentration and thinking, while alpha waves usually occur when the mind is in a relatively relaxed state. However, it is important to remember that the interpretation of these results depends on the specific research context, the experimental conditions, and the individual factors of the participants. Further research and analysis are needed to fully understand the full context

of these phenomena and their potential implications. We conducted this small study as a preliminary investigation to lay the groundwork for a comprehensive investigation aimed at understanding whether the use of virtual reality triggers anxiety and stress.

Conclusion

Four studies are examined in this paper, each of which uses EEG measurements as a means of investigating the relationship between virtual reality and stress. To make this clearer, we have summarized all the types of EEG waves and their meaning: Theta, Alpha, Beta 0, Beta 1, Beta 2, and Gamma. In the review of four articles published in recent years, they conclude that VR may cause stress for participants because of the sensory and mental stimulation required to experience VR. Although there are many barriers to using VR and EEG measurement tools, more experiments need to be tested in the future in different environments.

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